

Cultural Gems in the Fictions of Chinua Achebe and Mulk Raj Anand

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Abstract: The present research paper focuses on the interrelationship and interconnection between Culture and Literature, features, and the influential role of culture in literary creations; literature offers a platform to expose the conscious and subconscious thoughts, feelings and ideas. Cultural sense constantly exists in the mind of every individual, and intentionally or unintentionally the cultural doctrine of the artist peeps through his artistic creations, sometimes to express his inner voice and sometimes to communicate about his community. In the case of Achebe and Anand, literature has become a strong gizmo through which they have promoted their cultures and traditions, and attested the fact that their societies are not uncivilized, but possess an ancient cultural heritage. Their fictions illustrate that Nigeria and India have gracious and superior ethnic values.

Key Words: Multifaceted, Phenomena, Multidimensional, Ethos, Illustrate Essence, Polytheistic, Polygamy, Nurture, Ethically, Assault.

Introduction:

In the history of human civilization, culture and literature have been playing a substantial role. They are interrelated and interconnected; the former is multidimensional and multifaceted social phenomena and the latter incorporates artistic, factual, imaginative creations and recreations. According to E. B. Tylor, "Culture is that complex whole which includes knowledge belief, art, moral, law, custom and of any other capabilities acquired by man as a member of society"¹ He considers that culture is complex concept and the member of the particular culture has to adopt certain codes and norms. Cooley, Argell & Carr in their book, *Introductory Sociology*, discuss about culture in detail. They define culture as:

Culture is the entire accumulation of artificial object, conditions, tools, techniques, ideas, symbols and behaviour patterns peculiar to a group of people possessing a certain consistency of its own and capable of transmission from one generation to another.²

The above definitions point out that culture has some unique features, such as, it is shared by all the members of the society, it is not in born or innate, it is learned and acquired, the elements of culture are interrelated and constitute a complex whole; culture is transmitted from one generation to another generation, it is materialistic as well as non-materialistic; it is something like a chair, a fan or a car and abstract like belief or superstition. Culture is not static; it has the quality of adaptability. The formation and continuity of culture is not depending on any one individually, and it is collected ethos of the society. It is a social system of

common heritage, and it is integral part of the society. The culture of people is revealed in their beliefs, rituals, festivals, customs, traditions, symbols, norms, values dresses, food, works, languages and other actives.

Literature, as an art form includes fiction, non-fiction drama, and poetry, in which language is used as a medium to design an image to depict cultural life, as well as the perspectives of the author; culture is the source for literary creations. Chinua Achebe and Mulk Raj Anand have used literature, especially novels as a device to illustrate cultural dignity of their societies. Achebe, considering himself as the spokesman of Igbo clan, has presented the cultural identity along with the colonial confrontation and Anand has attempted to display the cultural essence and ethical ethos of the Indian life.

Truly outstanding in his literary achievements, Chinua Achebe exhibits a portrait of the past and present of African society. It is his conscious endeavor to present the African sensibility and atmosphere, because he realized that only an African can tell about Africanness, he states, "...the story we had to tell could not be told for us by anyone else no matter how gifted or well-intentioned."³ According to him the western world needs to know real Africa, he thought it is extremely important to set right the deeply embedded misconceptions about the African people. Through his novels he has tried to display "...that there nothing disgraceful about the African weather, that the palm tree is equally fit subject for poetry."⁴ It shows that Achebe has certain aims and aspirations in writing the novels; the culture of the Igbo clan has played a vital role in quenching his thirst of showing the identity of real Africans.

Similarly, Mulk Raj Ananda an Indian novelist, has revealed exceptional insight in interpreting the Indian socio-cultural life, his novels are the authentic documentation of the pains and pleasure of humanity. He too has a purpose, literature for him is also not for entertainment but to manifest the cultural values along with the agonies imposed on the deprived and oppressed class in India. He considered literature as an instrument, and through it, he has presented the galleries of realistic pictures of Indian ethical and cultural life of Indians. He says, "I have always considered literature and art as the instrument of humanism."⁵ He firmly believes:

... that only in fiction, which is the transformation, through the imagination, of concrete life, in words, sounds and vibrations, one may probe into the many layers of human consciousness with various phases... the writer can evolve an organic pattern, showing the efforts of human being to grow...⁶

Both Achebe and Anand have looked at literature as the cosmic canvas on which they have tried to interpret socio-cultural, political, spiritual, and economical aspects of Africa and India. In the present research paper the research scholar has selected Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Anand's *Two Leaves and a Bud* to illustrate the role of culture in literature, especially in the novels.

Things Fall Apart (1958), the masterpiece of Achebe illustrates the fact that culture is an inseparable segment of literature; the novel mirrors the cultural identity of the people through the multidimensional panorama of the Igbo society. It shows that Igbo society has great cultural past to boast of, like any other ancient civilization of the world. Umuofia, the village described in the novel represents Nigeria, is held together by network of relationships, with a common recognition, much stronger than any European civilization, the misinterpretation of African society by the western writers is appropriately countered in the novel. Okonkwo, the protagonist of the novel exemplifies that they are not barbarians and inhuman, on the contrary they are tender and compassionate at heart it is revealed in the case of Ikemefuna, a hostage boy. Traditionally, the Igbo community is male dominated, so Okonkwo sticks to its norms, codes and conducts, being famous for wrestling and for masculine qualities and having deeply rooted feeling of fear to show tender and female qualities can't stop himself from showing love for Ikemefuna, as the custom he kills Ikemefuna,

but being a human he is deeply disturbed. Achebe writes,

Okonkwo did not taste food for two days after the death... he did not sleep at night. He tried to think about Ikemefuna, but the more he tried the more he thought about him... But he was so weak that his legs could hardly carry him... a cold shiver descended on his head and spread down his body.⁷

The man of heroic qualities and afraid of nothing falls apart after doing a cruel act, it is the sign of well-developed civilization. The way of treating the guest also shows the reality that the community is cultured and well-mannered. When guest arrive to the Okonkwo's Obi he offers them traditional kola nuts and palm wine. He has great respects for his clan brother, he firmly believes in the principles of ancestors. He says, "As our people say. A man who pays respect to the great paves the way for his own greatness. I have come to you pay my respect."⁸ The respect for elders and ancestors is the notable feature of the Igbo culture and Achebe has demonstrated it throughout the novel.

Achebe shows that the Igbo community assigns key role to the women for instance, women painted the houses of the Egwugwu, the goddess, They are primary educator of children, through strong telling and behaviour, inspiring in them the curiosity about social values, relationships and the human conditions, the stories the women narrate also develop the artistic consciousness of the children in addition to entertain them. Furthermore the first wife of a man in the Igbo society is paid some respect. It is illustrated in the palm wine ceremony at Nwakibie's Obi, Anasi, Nwakibie's first wife had not yet arrived and the other wives did not drink still her arrival.

The position of the woman in the community is exposed at the time of exile of Okonkwo; the motherland is respected more than the fatherland in Igbo society. At the arrival of Okonkwo to his motherland, Okonkwo's uncle Uchendu noting Okonkwo's distress, eloquently explains the supremacy of mother. He says: A man belongs to his fatherland and not to his motherland. And yet we say Nneka- "mother is supreme. Why is that? It is true that a child belongs to its father but when a father beats his child it seeks sympathy in its mother's hut. A man belongs to his fatherland when things are good and life is sweet. But when there is sorrow and bitterness he finds refuge in his motherland. Your mother is there to perfect you and that is why we say that mother is supreme"⁹

The religious practices are the unified component of Igbo culture, Achebe has discussed in detail about the polytheistic religion practiced in Igbo culture, the Igbo people have different deities such as *Chukwu*, the supreme god, *Agbala*, the god of the future, *Ani*, the goddess of the earth and harvest, spirits and the ancestors, and they also have the concept of *Chi* which refers personal gods, the Igbos have polygamy system, it was considered a sign of prosperity of the man, a man with multiple wives is supposed to be successful, Okonkwo has three wives, in marriage is regarded a sacred union of two families, it is done with certain traditions and customs, such as giving the bride price from the side of the girl to the groom's family. They use bundles of broomsticks to negotiate the bride price. Farming is another aspect of in Igbo society, *Yams* is the main crop taken by the Igbos, it is brought in the compound after harvesting, if it excessive, it also sold in the market, they celebrate the "Week of Peace" in respect to the earth goddess, during the week Igbos visits their neighbors, they drink palm wine, sing folk- songs, and dance on the beating of traditional drums.

The place of woman in Igbo culture is not secondary. The saying, 'mother is supreme', by Unchendu to Okonkwo is the evidence that they bestow the great honour on a woman. The eldest wife is the head of women folk and have authority is exhibited in their custom of permitting her to wear the anklets of her husband's titles. Anasi, the eldest wife of Nakibie, is called by her husband and given a horn of palm wine before the others have their turn, in consideration of women's place in Igbo society, Michel Faber states. Women never saw themselves as secondary of inferior in traditional Ibo society. They were different that is all... in fact, when a man died, he was taken to his mother's people to be buried, that showed the importance of mother and woman. Also on the economic level the market has always been there for the women to make money and they had grown in importance. In traditional Ibo society the wife was economically independent.¹⁰

Anand's *Two Leaves and a Bud* is an artistic work, it mainly deals with the widening gap between the haves and have-nots, the rulers and the ruled, the owners and the workers, but along with the clash between the two classes, from the perspectives of British the Indians are not civilized. The novelist states, "as compared with their masters the, Indians were shocking barbarians in point of intellect and civilization."

¹¹Anand has insisted on the need for values, the civilizing values which nurture an enlightened and humane society. The novel presents the cultural supremacy of Indian society. He has shown that morally and ethically the Indians are far better than the British. Gangu a Panjabi farmer, along with his wife Sajani, his daughter and son Laila and Buddhu enlists as a worker in the Assam tea plantations. As the laborer, he is exploited and harassed by the colonizers, but he struggles to keep his family intact, Anand suggest that nothing the so precious than the family and the dignity of family members in the Indian culture,

The marriage is not just a formality; it is the amalgamation of two souls, husband and wife are the two wheels of the chariot of the home, in Indian society marriage is blessed and sacred union, Gangu is not only the husband of Sajani, he is "companion of her life and death."¹² She decides to help her husband in every situation of life; her family is above all, she cares for her daughter and son, when Sajani is on death bed, her mind is haunted by the cares for the daughter's marriage, and even after her death, Leila's mind is haunted by the memories of her mother, Gangu, as a true companion, "wept bitterly...he sat choked and convulsed by the agony, the intense misery, the utter helplessness of his despair."¹³ It shows that the family members are so intimate and connected to each other and they can go to any extent to help each other, it found only in the civilized community. Anand has pointed out that the head of the family can sacrifice everything to save the dignity and the ethics of the woman in India, and Gangu is the best example of it, Ruggie Hunt is fascinated to the beauty of Laila and he is after her like a hunter behind a bird, though Gangu is helpless and poor but he sacrifices himself to prevent the virginity of his daughter. Anand deliberately reveals this virtuous side of Indian society; he indirectly suggests that the British man may consider superior "because of his clothes, respected for his knowledge and admired for his personal qualities"¹⁴ but culturally, virtually and morally Indians are far superior to them.

Anand has demonstrated the cultural greatness of Indian people. The European officers also accepted the fact that Indian people have great sense of manners, but they do not admire it, on the contrary they ridicule it. Indians give great respect to the quests, the quests are considered as the gods. They are respected and the Indians are so hospitable to their quests, but the British officers like De La Harve thinks that

the Indians are stupid, because they are hospitable. He says, "These Indians are bloody fools, they are so hospitable, they let themselves be robbed... Shah Jehan's daughter is ill. An English doctor attends her. The Emperor gives away valuable forts in reward."¹⁵ actually, it is the age old custom of Indian people to treat the guest as if he is a god. Anand has unfolded the glorious sides of Indians in his fictions. His Indian upbringing and familiarity with Indian rich cultural heritage has given him the opportunity to write about his own people so authentically. His knowledge of western philosophy and life style has enabled him to present the variations between Indian culture and British culture, the values and norms of two countries. While presenting Indian culture as suppressed by British people, Anand throws light on Indian family values. He talks about the glorious side of Indian cultural norms. The home in Indian culture is not the building of four walls, it is much more than that, it is a place of love and comfort, and it is a protection place for women. She gives solace and strength to all the family members, all the family members wait for each other to dine together. These qualities are not found in the European homes. Anand gives importance to the family. It is true that women are more liberal in European families, Maya is also aware of this fact, those women choose their men freely in Vilayat, but Lalu thinks that if he would allow her to think and behave like British women the family set up of his life will be no more.

Both Achebe and Anand have considered literary writing as a mission to stimulate the masses to esteem the indigenous cultural gems and present the panorama of their ancient and proud cultural immensity to those who discredited and disgraced it, they successfully and strategically developed the thematic content to convey the message that Africa and India have great historical, spiritual and cultural roots, which are deeply imbedded and still survived even after the several assaults of the outsiders.

References/ Web References:

1. Achebe, Chinua. *Things Fall Apart*, Google, Web.10 Jan. 2019
- 2.. <https://www.wikipedia.org>
- 3.. [http://www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Two_Leaves and a Bud](http://www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Two_Leaves_and_a_Bud)
4. <http://www.contemporarywriters.com>
5. [https://www. Britanica.com](https://www.Britanica.com)
1. Tylor. E.B. *Primitive Culture*, Volume 1. London: John Murry, 1871. P.1
2. Cooley, Argall and Carr, *Introductory*

- Sociology*, New York: C. Scribner's Sons, 1933. P..519.
3. Achebe, Chinua. "The African Writer and the English Language", *Morning Yet On Creation Day: Essays*, London: Heinemann, 1975. P. 70.
4. Achebe, Chinua. "The Novelist as Teacher, " *Morning Yet On Creation Day: Essays*, London: Heinemann, 1975. P.44.
5. Anand, Mulk Raj. 'Why I Write?' in *Perspectives on Mulk Raj Anand*. ed. K.K. Sharma, Ghaziabad: VimalPrakashan, 1978), P.8.
6. *Ibid.*, P. 6.
7. Achebe, Chinua. *Things Fall Apart*. London: Heinemann, 1983. P. 57.
8. *Ibid.*, P. 18.
9. *Ibid.*, P. 122-123.
10. Faber, Michel. Chinua Achebe on *Arrow of God, The Literary Half Yearly*, XXI, 1, Jan.1980. P.6-7.
11. Anand, Mulk Raj, *Two Leaves and a Bud*. New Delhi: Hind Pocket Books (p) Ltd., 1983 .P.27.
12. *Ibid.*, P. 1.
13. *Ibid.*, P. 84.
14. *Ibid.*, P. 42.